

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BP'H) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Three rice varieties for release in Bombuwela

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Local variety Herath banda has three important characters improved varieties lack: exceptionally fast seedling growth, red pericarp and high palatability, and thrip resistance.

The 3-month strain BW 272-6B, bred to replace Herath banda, further consolidates high yield potential, resistance to lodging, high resistance to leaf blast, optimum yield at low levels of nitrogen, moderate resistance to salinity, high protein content (10-12.7%>), and suitability for mineral, half bog, and bog soils.

In farmers' fields BW 272-6B yielded twice as much as Herath banda. The average yield of Herath banda is 1.0-1.3 t/ha. The expected average yield of BW 272-6B is 2.6 t/ha, with a yield potential

of more than 4.6 t/ha.

Because more emphasis has been placed on the selection of early-maturing strains, BW 267-3 and BW 266-7 have recently emerged from the Bombuwela varietal improvement program.

BW 267-3 takes 108 days from sowing to maturity. It has a culm length of 74 cm and because of a fast early growth rate, its weed competitive ability is high. It is nonlodging. The grain is long and the pericarp color is white. It is highly resistant to blast, iron toxicity, grain spotting, and moderately resistant to bacterial blight and sheath blight.

BW 266-7 takes 102 days from sowing to maturity. It is 4-5 cm shorter than BW 267-3. It is nonlodging and has white, long, slender, translucent grain of high quality. Even ripening and clean crop are characteristic features. The strain is highly resistant to blast and grain spotting and moderately susceptible to bacterial blight and sheath blight. It is highly resistant to gall midge. ■

Performance of IRRI cultivars in Afghanistan

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Testing exotic varieties has been the main activity of the rice improvement program in Afghanistan. By 1979, 510 IRRI cultivars had been obtained, either directly from IRRI or from IRTP nurseries. Separate trials for fine-grained and coarse-grained cultivars were conducted at Jalalabad (eastern zone) and Baghlan (northern zone) 1971-80. No trials could be arranged in Herat (western zone). One local fine-grained variety — Barah at Baghlan and Pashadi, Lawangin or Behsudi at Jalalabad — was included as a check. Coarse-grained cultivars were compared with the local variety LUK at both sites.

Table 1. Performance of fine-grained IRRI cultivars in varietal trials at Jalalabad and Baghlan, Afghanistan.

Culture	Yield	Increase	
			%
<i>Jalalabad</i>			
IR1529-680-3-2	7.3	4.6	165.3
Local variety	2.8		
IR1561-228-3-6	6.2	3.6	143.0
Local variety	2.6		
IR1561-238-2	6.8	3.3	94.6
Local variety	3.5		
IR1628-632-1	7.6	4.6	156.7
Local variety	3.0		
IR1721-11-6-8-3-2	7.3	4.8	193.9
Local variety	2.5		
<i>Baghlan</i>			
IR1529-680-3-2	6.0	0.8	15.6
Local variety	5.2		
IR1561-228-3-3	7.3	1.8	32.6
Local variety	5.5		
IR1561-238-2	6.4	1.2	22.4
Local variety	5.2		